

**ACQUIRING INTERCULTURAL COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE FROM
COURSEBOOKS: AN ANALYSIS OF READING ACTIVITIES IN THE
COURSEBOOK “SPEAKOUT”**

**KÜLTÜRLERARASI İLETİŞİMSEL YETERLİLİĞİN DERS
KİTAPLARINDAN EDİNİMİ: “SPEAKOUT” DERS KİTABINDAKİ OKUMA
AKTİVİTELERİNİN KÜLTÜRLERARASI İLETİŞİMSEL YETERLİLİK
UNSURLARI AÇISINDAN ANALİZİ**

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Abstract

Intercultural communicative competence is recently considered to be a significant paradigm in language teaching area with the increasing role of English as a global lingua franca, therefore the integration of language and culture has become progressively more important. Since the textbooks are regarded as core teaching materials in foreign language teaching, it is essential for textbooks to contain various intercultural elements in order to construct the way for the development of intercultural communicative competence of learners. In this respect, intercultural content in English textbooks is a necessary issue to be investigated. This present study is an attempt to explore whether intercultural elements persist in language textbooks of Adana Science and Technology University School of Foreign Languages. As a result of the evaluation, it was found that textbook series of Speakout is not sufficient to enhance learners' intercultural communicative competence through its content in terms of reading activities.

Keywords: communicative competence, intercultural communicative competence, language teaching, textbook, textbook evaluation

Özet

İngilizcenin küresel ortak dil anlamındaki artan rolü ile kültürlerarası iletişimsel yeterlilik son zamanlarda dil öğretimi alanında önemli bir paradigma olarak kabul edilmektedir, bu nedenle dil ve kültür entegrasyonu giderek daha önemli hale gelmiştir. Ders kitapları yabancı dil öğretiminde temel öğretim materyalleri olarak değerlendirildiğinden, öğrencilere kültürlerarası iletişimsel yeterlilik gelişiminde yol inşa etmesi için çeşitli kültürler arası unsurları içermesi gereklidir. Bu bakımdan, İngilizce ders kitaplarında kültürlerarası içeriğin araştırılması gereklilik arz eden bir konudur. Bu çalışma, Adana Bilim ve Teknoloji Üniversitesi Yabancı Diller Yüksek Okulu'ndaki İngilizce ders kitaplarının kültürlerarası unsurları içerip içermediğini araştırmak için bir girişimdir. Değerlendirme sonunda, “Speakout” ders kitabı serisinin okuma faaliyetleri bakımından içeriği ile ilgili olarak öğrencilerin kültürlerarası iletişimsel yeterlilik becerilerini geliştirmek için yeterli olmadığı tespit edilmiştir.

Anahtar Kelimeler: iletişimsel yeterlilik, kültürlerarası iletişimsel yeterlilik, dil öğretimi, ders kitabı, ders kitabı değerlendirilmesi

1. Introduction

Today in the 21st century with the ease of communication, the advancements in information networks, and multiple purposes for travelling, countries have established a closer relationship with each other and the world has become smaller as a result of the development of globalization process. People are in a constant move from one country to another for various reasons such as pleasure, travel, academic study or working. These reasons and factors have resulted in increased opportunities for intercultural encounters. Consequently, contact of people from different cultures and countries made the importance of intercultural communication increase rapidly and inevitable in this century. With this mass cross-cultural interaction, one of the most common issues that the global world has encountered is the phenomenon of multiculturalism. Since we have to be in contact with different people from different parts of the world constantly, it is vital to have an intercultural understanding for successful communications. In this respect, people need to tolerate the existence of other cultures and they need to have acceptance, empathy, positive feelings, towards cultural differences without prejudices. Troncoso (2010) states in his study that dealing with the diversity of ethnic, racial, religious or intercultural changes may be possible by means of intercultural communicative competence (ICC). ICC is defined as an ability to understand other cultures as well as your own and having successful communication interactions; it is a complex of abilities needed to perform effectively and appropriately when interacting with others who are linguistically and culturally different from oneself (Fantini, 2006, p.12). It is possible to provide an intercultural understanding with the help of the education. For this to occur, we need to reconstruct our education system with the framework of intercultural competence which is the ability for understanding of other people's feeling, thinking, perception, and acting. Foreign language education is concerned with teaching of intercultural competence since in foreign language classes learners are exposed to various types of world cultures. In foreign language teaching process, as the teaching materials and course books are important tools, they are expected to provide intercultural elements to foster intercultural communicative competence of learners. Especially in multicultural learning environment, such as universities, the course book carries a significant importance as there might be students from different national and cultural backgrounds. As a consequence, illustrations of the multicultural components in the content of the coursebook in terms of ICC are expected criteria in the course books to foster intercultural understanding for the learners. In this thesis it is aimed to analyze the coursebooks in terms of developing intercultural communicative competence for language learners. With this aim, the research questions of this present study are as follows;

1. To what extent do the coursebooks *Speakout A2+* and *B1+* contain reading parts aimed at developing learners' intercultural communicative competence?
2. What dimensions of intercultural communicative competence, if any, do the reading parts of the respective coursebooks address?

2. Methodology

In this study, the descriptive content analysis was conducted to make an in-depth description of the course book *Speakout* in terms of including or not including intercultural elements. According to Seliger and Shohamy (1990, p. 211) a

descriptivestudy model provides information about how often certain language phenomena occur and the typical use of language elements are demonstrated in accordance with the various variables which can be used in the studies of language teaching. The aim of this type of study is to obtain information concerning the current status of the phenomena to describe what exists with respect to conditions in a situation.

As stated before, our aim is to evaluate the global course book *Speakout* in terms of analysing intercultural elements in language materials. In this study, the researcher used a framework that was originally proposed by Byram (1991) but modified and improved into a checklist by Aijala (2009) and it aims to evaluate the coursebook for analysis of intercultural elements in reading activities. The checklist (Aijala, 2009) organizes intercultural elements into four dimensions: *knowledge of others, attitudes towards cultures, interpreting and relating cultural elements, intercultural interaction*.

➤ **Knowledge of Others:** *Knowledge of social groups and their products and practices in one's own and in one's interlocutor's country, and of the general processes of societal and individual interaction.* This title includes;

- knowledge of social processes and knowledge of illustrations
- knowledge about other people and how other people perceive you
- knowledge of discovering new information about culture of others', e.g. verbal and non-verbal behaviours and daily life

➤ **Attitudes Towards Cultures:** *Curiosity and openness, readiness to suspend disbelief about other cultures and belief about one's own.* This title involves;

- to be able to aware of one's own values and beliefs and to be able to see them from others' perspective who have different beliefs and behaviours
- to be able to positive, open-minded and curious for familiar or unfamiliar phenomena

➤ **Interpreting and Relating Cultural Elements:** *Ability to interpret a document or event from another culture, to explain it and relate it to documents or events from one's own.* This title includes abilities to;

- recognise the clues of behaviour in different settings in other cultures
- identify areas of ethnocentric perspectives that each different cultural system presents

➤ **Intercultural Interaction:** *Ability to acquire new knowledge of a culture and cultural practices and the ability to operate knowledge, attitudes and skills under the constraints of real-time communication and interaction.* This title involves the ability to

- interact with representatives of other cultures
- to mediate for confusing interpretations of phenomena.

3. Data Analysis and Results

3.1. The Ratio of ICC Elements Provided in the Reading Activities in Each CourseBook

Regarding the first research question, the findings are described as following.

Research Question 1: To what extent do the coursebooks *Speakout A2+* and *B1+* contain reading parts aimed at developing learners' intercultural communicative competence?

To obtain an answer for the first research question, the reading texts in two English coursebook series of *Speakout* were analysed in order to find out whether the reading texts were aimed at increasing students' intercultural communicative competence focused on in the current study. Regarding the evaluation, it was found that *Speakout A2+* has 56 reading parts and *Speakout B1+* has 64 reading parts in total. However, *Speakout A2+* level has 5 intercultural communicative elements and *Speakout B1+* level has 4 intercultural communicative elements in their reading parts. When we proportion the total number of reading parts related to intercultural communicative competence, we get B1 (intermediate) level book has the least level ratio (6,2 %). The other A2 (pre-intermediate) level book has the highest ratio (8,9%) when the total number of elements are evaluated. The total ratio of the two coursebook is (7,5%).

Table 1

The ratio of the evaluated reading parts

	Total Number of Tasks Evaluated	Tasks Related to Intercultural Communicative Competence	%
B1 (Intermediate)	64	4	6,2
A2 (Pre-Intermediate)	56	5	8,9
Total	120	9	7,5

Regarding the evaluation of the reading parts, the illustrative examples from the parts in the coursebook related to ICC are as the following. Considering the sentences of the first reading part that reflects the *factual knowledge of culture*; they can be regarded as examples for this objective in terms of increasing awareness and cultures of other people and countries. "Holiday 10 best takes a journey to different cities around the world to find out what they have to offer. They go to coolest, hippest, biggest and most exciting places on the planet and discover what makes a city truly great" (Speakout, 2012).

When we evaluate the other reading text of the textbook for the same objective of *factual knowledge of cultures*, the following sentence of the reading text can be given as an example for this objective since it helps learners to have an understanding and an idea for foreign societal and cultural events and general process of lifestyles. "In 2008 Monocle Magazin looked at cities around the world to find the ten best cities to live in" (Speakout, 2012).

In terms of the objective of *collecting information on cultures*, the coursebook presents two reading texts which are culture quiz for the students. "Which painting was upside down for two months in New York's Museum of Modern Art before anyone noticed?" (Speakout, 2012). This is one of the questions of the culture quiz and it can be shown as an example for this objective. In this way, the students are able to increase their knowledge of foreign cultures by using sources outside the coursebook material which is an aim of the objective. The other

reading text of the coursebook presents another culture quiz which is an example for the same objective of *collecting information on cultures*. “Which charismatic scientist spent his free time playing the violin when he was not changing the world?” (Speakout, 2012).

Considering this question of the quiz, it is seen that it invites learners to collect information and increase their knowledge for other cultures which is another aim of this objective. In terms of the objective of *identifying generalisations of cultures* the coursebook involves two reading texts. Considering its sentences and questions of the first reading text of the coursebook, the following lines can be given as examples since it invites learners to express their impressions and attitudes concerning foreign cultures, which is an aim of the objective. “There, he learns about their traditions and discovers how the community survives. There are just twenty-four families on Anuta. Bruce meets them all and experiences how their customs help to bind the people together.” “What do you think life is like for people on an island like this? Would you like to visit this place? Why or Why not?” (Speakout, 2012). There is one more reading text presented in the book for the same objective *identifying generalisations of cultures*. Regarding the sentences and the questions of the reading text, it is seen that they can be considered as examples for this objective as it invites students to state their opinions and impressions about others. “Micheal Palin is an actor and travel writer. In this programme, he went on a journey through these seventeen countries along the Pasific coast. While travelling 5000 miles in ten months, he saw and discovered things beyond his dreams. He learnt how to cook eggs in a volcano and how to make music with horses’ bones in Chile.” “What do you think of this journey? Would you like to do it? Why? Why not?” (Speakout, 2012).

In terms of the objective of *identifying ethnocentric perspectives* the textbook gives a reading text and informs about a famous painter around the world. When we consider questions, it is seen that the students are asked to identify ethnocentric perspectives of a product of a foreign culture that reflects one of the aims of this objective. “This BBC documentary examines the life and work of Michelangelo, one of the greatest artists in history; an imperfect life can produce perfect art.” “What do you think of Michelangelo’s work? Have you ever seen any of his work? How do you think his work has influenced other artists?” (Speakout, 2012).

Regarding the objective of *relating cultures and cultural phenomena*, the coursebook presents one reading text and the following statements can be given as examples of this objective. “In Osaka, people love life and they love their food and they love to spend money on food. So, what about you? Which city is your culinary favourite?” (Speakout, 2012). Considering these statements of the text, we see that it invites learners to relate features of foreign cultures to one’s own and ponder on similarities and differences of cultures by reflecting their personal views as an aim of this objective. The textbook presents one reading text that includes the objective of *identifying and explaining causes of misunderstandings* in the following lines. “Durrels family sell their house and move to the sunny island of Corfu in Greece. Here they experience a new life of freedom and adventure. But the beginning is not easy.” “Have you ever tried to communicate with people who can not speak your language? Where do tourists like to go when they visit your country? What problems do they have?” (Speakout, 2012). Regarding the statements and the questions of the reading text, they can be

shown as the examples of this objective since the learners are invited to identify areas potential misunderstandings and dysfunction in interaction that is an aim of this objective.

3.2. The Ratio of ICC Dimensions Provided in the Reading Activities in Each Course Book

Regarding the second research question, the findings are described as following.

Research Question 2: What dimensions of intercultural communicative competence, if any, do the reading parts of the respective coursebooks address? When these reading parts containing intercultural communicative competence elements were analyzed in order to find out which ICC dimension is mostly focused on as stated in the second research question, it was found that out of nine reading parts, four of them (3,3%) were aiming at improving the students' *knowledge of cultures*. Three reading parts (2,5%) were aiming at improving *interpreting and relating cultural elements*. In terms of the *attitudes towards cultures*, only two (1,6%) reading parts were found which belong to that dimension. However, it was seen that the coursebook does not give place to the dimension *intercultural interaction* (0%) as there was no reading parts belong to this dimension. The following sections analyses the findings in categories.

Figure 1

Findings Obtained From the Checklist

3.3. Knowledge of Cultures

Reading parts in this dimension invite learners to develop understanding of the term culture. It requires being aware of one's own and other foreign cultures and general processes of societal and individual interaction. *Knowledge of Cultures* was divided under the titles of *Factual Knowledge of Cultures*, *Understanding the Concept of Culture* and *Collecting Information on Cultures*.

In terms of the objective of *Factual Knowledge of Cultures*, the course book gives two reading texts about world's cities. The aim of this objective is to increase learners' (own or foreign) knowledge of culture specific events, products, significant individuals and emblems, conventions of communication and interaction, private and public institutions or national memory. In this regard, in the first reading text the students are informed about one of the most popular city in the world. The text addresses the city for its sightseeing places, leisure time activities, food and culture events. Regarding this, the students are asked questions and they are supposed to comment and discuss the related issues of the city. In this way, the learners are able to increase their awareness and knowledge of other cultures and people. (Unit 3.4)

The second reading text that reflects the same objective of *factual knowledge of cultures* informs about world's well-known cities. The students are able to have general knowledge for the people, city life, social activities and culture of those different cities in this way. The questions of reading text help learners for being aware of other foreign societal and cultural events and general process of different lifestyle as an aim of this objective. (Unit 10.1)

The second objective *Understanding the Concept of Culture* helps to increase learners' knowledge for the different ways of defining culture and the ways that it affects culture and communication. When the course book is evaluated on the basis of this objective, there is no reading text that meets the criteria of the objective. Hence, it is seen that the course book does not give importance to defining cultures and its effects for communication in terms of this objective.

Two reading parts are given in the course books that reflect the objective of *Collecting Information on Cultures*. This objective invites learners to collect information and increase their knowledge of own and/or foreign cultures. In this sense, a culture quiz was given to the students and they were expected to choose correct answer of the questions that belonged to various different cultures. (Unit 3.2)

In terms of same objective *Collecting Information on Cultures*, the book presents another culture quiz about famous people in history around the world. The students are asked to answer related questions and in this way they are supposed to gather information and increase their knowledge about different cultures. (Unit 9.3)

3.4. Attitudes towards Cultures

This dimension of checklist invites learners to be able to aware of one's own values and to be able to see from others' perspective. *Attitudes Towards Cultures* were divided under the titles of *Identifying Generalisations of Cultures* and *Changing Perspectives*. In terms of the objective of *Identifying Generalisation of Cultures* there are two reading texts in the book. This objective invites learners to express their opinions, impressions and show attitudes concerning own and/or different foreign cultures. The first reading text is about one of the most remote communities on earth. The text informs about their traditions, culture and lifestyle; and how their customs help to bind those people together. The learners are supposed to answer the questions and Express their impressions of that culture journey for that different community. They are expected to express their opinions for that country and its people culture, language, and custom. The questions make learners become aware of different countries, their language,

their lifestyle, food, habits and culture. Therefore, as stated in the objective of *identifying generalisations of cultures* this reading part invites learners to express their opinions and show attitudes concerning different foreign cultures. (Unit 8.4)

In terms of same objective *Identifying Generalisations of Cultures*, there is one more reading text presented in the course book. It is about a travel writer and his journey through the seventeen countries along the Pacific coast. The text gives placesome remote cities and countries and their special traditions, customs and all the things which represent them. The students are asked to express their views about those cities, people, country and travel journey. (Unit 5.4)

The objective of *Changing Perspectives* invites learners to change perspective, empathise with foreign points of view and relativise one's own cultural viewpoint. In the process of evaluation it was seen that there is no reading part that meets the criteria of this subcategory.

3.5. Interpreting and Relating Cultural Elements

Interpreting and relating cultural elements dimension aims to acquire the ability to interpret a document or event from another culture, to explain it and relate it to documents or events from one's own. It was divided under the titles of *Identifying Ethnocentric Perspectives*, *Relating Cultures and Cultural Phenomena*; and *Identifying and Explaining Causes of Misunderstandings*.

The objective of *identifying ethnocentric perspectives* asks the learners to identify ethnocentric perspectives of products such as paintings, films, texts, practises or events of own/foreign culture. In this sense, a reading text is given about the life and works of famous painter Michelangelo and the students are supposed to interpret and discuss the related questions. (Unit 9.4)

When the course book evaluated in terms of *Relating Cultures and Cultural Phenomena*, there is one reading text that meets the criteria of this objective. The idea of this objective invites learners to ponder on similarities and differences of foreign/own cultures or to reflect their personal encounters or to relate features of own/foreign cultures. The reading text presents different traditional food from different countries but especially focuses on one country. The learners are invited to reflect their views about those cultural food of the countries. (Unit 10.2)

The last objective of *identifying and explaining causes of misunderstandings* invites learners to identify areas of misunderstandings and dysfunction in interaction and explain them in terms of the cultural systems in present. In this sense, a reading text is given about a British family who decides to sell their house in England and moves to an island of Greece. The learners are asked questions about the problems that the family experience as a result of facing with cultural differences of the two countries. (Unit 7.4)

3.6. Intercultural Interaction

This dimension aims to acquire new knowledge of a culture and cultural practices and the ability to operate knowledge, attitudes and skills under the constraints of real-time communication and interaction. This dimension were divided under the titles of *Functioning as a Mediator Between Cultures and Dealing with Conflict Situations* and *Applying one's*

Abilities in Interaction. When the coursebook is examined in terms of this dimension, it is seen that there is no reading part that meets the related objective and no example to illuminate this dimension. It is easily realised that the coursebook does not give much importance to the dimension of *intercultural interaction*.

As a result of the evaluation, it is seen that the objectives in the dimensions partially meet the need for developing ICC of learners. Regarding the analysis and findings of the study, the reading parts of this textbook at two levels are not a good example for ICC and it is not possible to say that the textbook series of *Speakout* is sufficient to enhance learners' intercultural communicative competence through its content in terms of reading parts.

4. Discussion and Conclusion

The role of English as *a lingua franca* points out that English does not belong to any nation or society, therefore it is owned not only by native speakers but also other individuals speaking English as second language. Le (1998) state that even though most EFL learners have good linguistic competence, they still encounter communicative difficulties due to lack of sociolinguistic competence (Geeslin, et al., 2018). Moreover, they are not able to realize that each language differs in its ways of conveying messages and feelings as many learners are not aware of the intercultural elements. Because of this fact that, learners are usually in the mistake of transferring their native language expressions inappropriately into the target language, it causes problems in communications. Rather than reflecting a specific culture in language teaching, learners should be given intercultural skills in order to be successful in a communicative situation. Alptekin (2002) supports the idea that taking the native speaker as a model and merely taking into account of the cultural aspects of the target culture may result in leaving the learner's own culture in a peripheral position or even ignoring it completely. Rather than focus on a specific culture model, it is much more convenient and useful to make

the learners acquire intercultural understanding in their learning environment to have successful interaction in our global era. In this regard, another scholar Auguliar (2008) points that a wide range of activities and studies were developed by the Council of Europe to be able to provide education that consists of intercultural understanding. The publication of "all different, all equal" which is an education pack including activities and resources for intercultural education can be given as an example for the efforts of CE on this issue. Therefore, it can be concluded that intercultural communicative competence is a significant issue which should be highlighted and integrated in ELT classes and teaching materials to provide intercultural understanding for language learners. Among the teaching materials, course books are main tools which guide the learning process in foreign language education. In order to achieve this goal, coursebooks should include not only target culture but also intercultural items. The current study was an attempt to shed light on how much ICC elements the course books provide for language learners at university preparation classes of Turkey. In order to achieve this purpose, the two levels of course books series *Speakout* were examined in terms of intercultural communicative competence which are used at Adana Science and Technology University. In this respect, all types of reading parts, including writing, speaking and listening skills, were taken into consideration for analyzing.

In order to find the answers of the research questions, each reading part of the two coursebooks was examined in order to find out if it could be categorised into at least one of

the dimensions of intercultural communicative competence such as *knowledge of cultures, attitudes towards cultures, interpreting relating cultural elements, or intercultural interaction*. This study dealt with all the reading parts and they were all gone through for detailed evaluation. All in all, *Speakout A2+* has 56 and *Speakout B1+* has 64 reading parts in total. However, in two course books there are only 9 intercultural elements in their reading parts. *Speakout A2+* contains 5 and *Speakout B1+* contains 4 intercultural reading parts separately. When we proportion the reading parts, we get the total ratio about (7,5 %). The finding shows that this ratio is not enough to develop intercultural understanding of the learners. As a result of the evaluation, it can be said that the reading parts of the coursebooks mostly addresses the dimension of *knowledge of cultures* with the ratio of (3,3%). This dimension makes contribution to learners to knowledge of discovering one's own and other cultures.

When the course books are evaluated in terms of *attitudes towards culture*, the ratio is only (1,6%) that refers to this dimension. Hence, the course books are not rich enough to invite learners for openness, being positive and readiness to suspend disbelief about other cultures as this dimension requires. The dimension of *interpreting and relating cultural elements* contributes to the ability to interpret an event or document from another culture and make relations to one's own. The ratio is (2,5%) addressing to aim of this dimension. Considering the percentage, the content is not sufficient to develop objectives of the dimension. Regarding *intercultural interaction*, the course books do not contain any reading part with the ratio of (0%) serving to purpose of this dimension. Therefore, the objectives of this dimension such as functioning as mediator between cultures and dealing with conflict situations or applying one's abilities in interaction can not be achieved by learners. The textbook has the most serious weakness in point of this objective.

All in all, the current study aimed to investigate the intercultural elements in reading texts in the coursebooks. This content analysis-based thesis aimed to find out the contribution to the understanding of to what extent university level language learners are exposed to intercultural elements by using coursebooks. All types of reading parts were taken into consideration while analyzing the coursebook. They were evaluated according to the objectives and criteria in the checklist. The number of reading parts included intercultural elements of these two levels of coursebook are not good examples of intercultural communicative competence. Considering the graphs, numerical statistics, analysis and in the light of the literature; findings indicate that the two levels of *Speakout* series reading content is not sufficient in the way of intercultural education. Therefore, educators need to take into consideration and give priority to intercultural elements while choosing the coursebooks.

Parallel to the conclusions of our study, another content analysis research by Korkmaz (2009) supports the view that there should be more intercultural item emphasis holistically in textbooks. In Turkey, many course books have some shortcomings in terms of intercultural elements such as *New Headway, Face to Face* and *New Cutting Edge* examined by Korkmaz (2009). In the content analysis of his study, he finds that the proportion of multicultural items seem to be little when compared to the items belonging to the target culture, the target culture items outweigh the intercultural ones. Thus, Korkmaz (2009) defends that it could be still early to say that all these coursebooks fully respond to the requisites of a curriculum which is oriented and designed in an intercultural approach in education.

In terms of the parallel conclusions to these content analysis-based studies, our research might contribute to the understanding of to what extent and how university level language learners are exposed to intercultural elements in foreign language teaching. In that regard, this thesis study might make a change of policy makers, teachers, and textbook writers in their perception of fostering ICC skills to learners through coursebooks in the field of language teaching.

Supporting our research, another content based study was carried out by Köroğlu (2013) to discover the perceptions of language instructors about the textbook content of *English for Life* in terms of fostering ICC. As a result of her study, Köroğlu (2013) explains that the evaluated textbook series is not sufficient to provide ICC through its content which is similar to our research findings.

Through the eyes of a language teacher, it is significant for a teacher to be able to choose and evaluate a coursebook from different points of view. A textbook should fit the needs of students and institute and provide sufficient examples of cultural and intercultural elements as well as linguistic ones. It should be kept in mind that, even if the content is not sufficient enough to foster ICC of learners, it is at the same time in teachers' hand to enrich the content for ICC skills and to guide the learners accordingly. Regarding this, teachers should be equipped with intercultural background to be able to realize this goal. In that point, ministry of education, policy makers and institutes should adapt their teacher trainings programmes appropriately to develop intercultural communicative competence as a necessity of intercultural education in globalization process of the world.

5. Implications

Since English continues to have the role of international language, one of the aims of foreign language teaching is considered to give learners intercultural communicative competence as well as language competence in a new and changing era of language education. It is a well-known fact that cultural elements and linguistic skills should be integrated in language learning and teaching for effective language proficiency. Obviously, language environment should expand the circles of successful intercultural communication as a requirement of a healthy interaction with others in a global context. In order to put this view into practice, as the most important language teaching materials the course books should contain elements of diversity of different cultures, in this way they can be in the expanding circle of intercultural education. In an attempt to create an intercultural atmosphere in a language classroom, course books are considered as the ways to different cultures through which language learners are advised to walk on. Language learners are able to see the world through the eyes of other individuals from different cultures. In addition to this, learners become "*diplomats*" of their own countries with the chances presented to them where they are able to give culture knowledge about their own communities (Corbett, 2003).

The present study suggests improvements for textbooks' content in terms of intercultural communicative competence and presentation of various intercultural elements as part of foreign language teaching. In this respect, as well as the linguistic competence, the content of the course books should be widened to broaden learners' perspectives and they should make contribution to their intercultural world view. The course books should help them to enhance their knowledge about different societies, social groups, countries; and they should

provide understanding to show tolerance to others; moreover, the course books should give an ability to interpret different worldviews; and also they should acquire the ability to mediate against confusing situations in a multicultural environment. A course book should include a collection of input supported by a variety of intercultural activities which are essential for learners to improve their perspectives. Considering the status of English as a *lingua franca*, textbooks should touch upon other countries instead of a specific target language culture. In this way, the learners might have a chance to compare different world cultures and they are able to raise their awareness for intercultural understanding. Living in a global era, international communication has become a significant issue to ensure successful global communication, and cross-cultural interaction has become an increasingly common aspect of human life. With this mass interaction, it is important to have intercultural understanding in today's global world. To achieve this, intercultural understanding should be adopted in education system and in foreign language teaching in order to have effective communications across cultures. As a consequence, since the course books are core teaching materials and the most efficient tools to develop skills of cultural and intercultural competence of learners in language classes, evaluating a course book from different points of view and choosing the most appropriate one is essential since the course books are supposed to fit the demands of 21st century language teaching.

6. Suggestions for Further Studies

In the present study, only two levels (A2 and B1) of the textbook series were selected in an attempt to evaluate the intercultural communicative competence elements in their content. A further research might be carried out with more levels or more different textbooks to be able to gather more precise conclusion. The scope of this study was restricted with the reading parts only. A further study focusing on other learning activities might be helpful for a more comprehensive evaluation of a textbook in terms of ICC. The present research might lead to a detailed content analysis of textbooks regarding ICC since the results are based on the data obtained from the reading part evaluation. In addition, teamwork could be more useful for the evaluation of the items in the textbook.

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